

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NGO NGOA****FIRST NAME: HERMINE GERALDE****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 3%

The author used the following software: (MSWord -Office 365 on Windows 11)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page numbers in the text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Process of academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. Some rules of thumb (EUCLID 2021, 14-16)
3. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15-22)
4. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-35)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
6. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I got refreshed on how to write an academic essay while going through the ACA-401-ACA/401D because it has been almost a decade since I was in school. This document lays down the criteria for an excellent academic essay and underlines the pivotal role of papers in the school curriculum, particularly in graduate programs. The fact that Euclid University puts this course at the beginning of this program is well thought out. I did all my studies, 70% in French and 30% in English (British English), on-site in Cameroon. I had to learn about American English when I moved to the USA, and I still have a lot to know now that I am using it in a formal setting. I also need to be more comfortable with technology; this online program will be challenging. Nevertheless, I am taking time to navigate the Euclid system, and I will be okay with the help of technical support and my instructors.

In this response paper, I will tackle the concepts of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course that need more of my attention: the process of writing an academic essay by respecting some rules of thumb, the use of appropriate punctuation, comparison between American and British English, how to make proper referencing and avoid plagiarism, and the importance of having style guides.

2) PROCESS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

To write an academic essay is to convince the reader of a position or eventuality through informed reasoning supported by evidence and analysis. This writing process has three main stages (EUCLID 2021, 7-10).

a) Stage of preparation

At the preparation stage, one needs to research and understand the assignment. The theme must be perfectly phrased, unambiguous, and concise. Elaborate a plan as a first draft that will put down your ideas and the result of your research. Then, a well-organized final plan will align with the basic structure of an essay: introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10).

b) Writing and revision

An essay starts with an introduction, where the writer must grab the reader's attention and inform them of what will be discussed in your paper. One needs, therefore, a hook in the first sentences, circumscribe the context, and explain some terms. Just enough to give a taste of the thesis. Then, provide the central argument and announce the structure of the essay.

The body part is the longest part of the essay. You make arguments to support your postulate, provide evidence, and develop your ideas here. Paragraphs are used to give a more explicit structure to your writing. Each section focuses on one idea and transitions between paragraphs, creating harmony. This part is also the place to explain and interpret data and materials and provide examples and quotes to develop your overall argument. After this long development, it will be time to wrap up and make a closing argument.

Conclusion is the place to summarize and tie the points you talked about together, to show the results of your hypothesis, and to emphasize the importance of the main argument. Then, you can proofread your first draft, revise it, and polish it by double-checking if your thesis was well stated and developed. Finally, check the grammar, spelling, and formatting and if some rules of thumb have been respected.

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB

I have understood that there are things a writer should never do and other things to always do in an academic essay. In terms of context, one must focus on the central theme to stay on the topic. It will also be good to avoid abstract principles and statements that are too general. One writing must be straightforward. Quotes from other writers must be used carefully to support ideas to avoid plagiarism. The form of your scripts is as important as the context.

I confirm that writing using short sentences, good transitions, and well-organized paragraphs will enhance the ideas you are expressing. Using coordinating conjunctions (for, and, nor, but, or, and so) at the beginning of a sentence is not allowed. Do not use abbreviations or contractions either. One must choose a suitable writing format as well. Formerly, in a French and British setting, I realized that America's print size, margins, and paragraph format are very different. Punctuation also plays a significant role in making a paper look harmonious.

4) PUNCTUATIONS

I understand punctuation better by reading this course pack and watching videos online. Punctuation gives the writing a rhythm, and misplaced punctuation can deteriorate the meaning of a sentence or a whole text. As it is said that short and simple sentences are the best way to go, this statement is also true for punctuation. Use as little punctuation as possible. Specific punctuation is still an issue for me, and I will need more attention to apostrophes and quotation marks. Where to use single or double quotation marks could have been clearer. Now, I know exactly that for possession, I must use an apostrophe before S after a singular noun and just an apostrophe after a plural noun ending with S. With compound nouns, the apostrophe is placed at the end of the final part. It is essential to know that 'it,' with the meaning of belonging, is 'its' without the apostrophe.

Single quotation marks are used for direct speech and double quotation marks for another quote in the exact quote. There is no need for quotation marks when the section is not in line with the rest of the text. I also realized that other punctuation with quotation marks must be inside the quotation marks if needed and outside if they do not belong to the quote (except closing punctuation if the section's end is also the sentence's end). All these English rules may vary according to the type of English used.

5) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

The difference between US and UK English was one of the cultural shocks I got when I arrived in the USA, and I am still updating until today. I realized that spoken and written US English and the UK differ. My challenging areas are pronunciation, some syntax, and, newly discovered in this course, US punctuation in quotations. I also need clarification and use both English versions in a text. Thanks to EUCLID, the differences in

usage, grammar, and pronunciation are so well explained in the course pack. I will now pay attention and only use American English. I will mostly be able to produce text in English on my own.

6) PLAGIARISM

“Nothing is new under the sun” (Ecclesiastes 1:9); as this phrase states, it is understood that there is no topic one can write that has never been spoken about. Nevertheless, authenticity is in how you put any information together. Sometimes, referencing others to support ideas in an essay is helpful. This task must be done carefully, and credit must be given to the sources one uses. I think citations and quotes also show how cultured the writer is. Balance is required, though; the writer must know how many quotations and sources to use so as not to overshadow his input. I am glad this course pack is giving me guidelines to avoid plagiarism and proposes a style guide to conform my writings to the purpose of the program and EUCLID standards.

7) STYLE GUIDE

Euclid University recommends a Turabian style guide (EUCLID 2021, 44). Style is a critical element in writing because it lets the writer inform the reader about the canal used to display the text on the paper. It also shows respect for the recommendations of the institution with which the paper’s author is affiliated. Chicago style is used at all levels of the writing process: abbreviations, page formatting, quotations, editing, and bibliography. I do not think I have used any style guide before; if so, I do not know which one exactly. I will consider this proposed style guide my first one and will properly refine its style and make it fit the level of writing needed.

8) CONCLUSION

An academic paper results from a process that encompasses a writing structure, respect for some rules, and appropriate language, style, and guidelines. Therefore, it is required that the student complete this complex task assiduously so the paper can reflect the level of education and his competencies. I will use this first-period course pack as my principal tool in writing and put more effort into familiarizing myself with online learning.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Bible Gateway. N.d. "Bible Gateway Passage: Ecclesiastes 1 - New International Version." Accessed December 27, 2023. <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Ecclesiastes%201&version=NIV>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.